

1 Quantitative and Qualitative Evaluation of
2 Transforming to Flipped-Classroom from
3 Instruction Teaching using Micro Feedback
4 Loops

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Abstract

Recently, the institutionalized transformation of frontal instruction classrooms into active learning spaces to foster the concept of (inter-)active learning has gained increasing attention. To investigate the impact of elements of active learning on learning reception of students in an advanced small sized MSc STEM course (<25 students), a traditional instructor teaching style class was transformed to flipped-classroom teaching. Before and after each lecture, anonymized evaluation Likert items from the students were recorded. Thus, both teaching styles for every given lecture were covered equally. In both classrooms, some didactic and methodological elements were kept constant, while others were changed when flipped-classroom took over semester midterm. Qualitative and quantitative results indicated that the flipped-classroom format generated greater learning effects as well as classroom enjoyment, fostered students' self-regulated learning, enhanced group interaction, stimulated group activity and guaranteed a more synergistic learning behavior.

Keywords: STEM, active learning transformation, frontal instructional teaching, flipped-classroom teaching, micro-feedback loops.

52 students' active contributions in the course of lectures is clearly much more challenging than just
53 reading a lecture frontally – it also comprises social learning about the target group. On the other
54 hand, students also have to invest more energy and time into active learning formats.

55 Two increasingly popular alternatives of active learning are problem-based Learning (PBL)
56 (Hung, Jonassen, & Liu, 2008) and flipped-classroom learning (FC) approach (Davidson, Major, &
57 Michaelsen, 2014). With regards to PBL, several universities already have transformed whole study
58 programs to be able to advertise and dominantly use the new format.^{1,2} Thus, with PBL being the
59 already more established method, FC needs more research to follow the success of PBL. Currently,
60 there is no university marketing with FC teaching around the globe. However increasingly,
61 institutions adopt the method into their curricula. The difference between FC and PBL is how and
62 which topics and holistic human cognitions and actions are focused. FC encourages students to take
63 over the responsible role of the teacher conveying curricular learning goals. PBL puts emphasis on
64 problem solving in small case studies in a study discussion and work group format (Tawfik & Lilly,
65 2015). In both formats students actively and creatively take part in the course lectures and act in a
66 social context as required in diversity- and gender-oriented teaching and especially later in their
67 professional life later on.

68 As indicated also from another point of view, the use of active learning methods actually
69 gets mandatory in the future classroom: The distraction of students by the new media environment
70 is an elephant in the room to be discussed and addressed. Facebook, Twitter and the like are a
71 challenging distraction, especially with large classes.

72 Here, in the proposed flipped-classroom course format, the students were encouraged to
73 bring their own devices such as laptops and use them for the benefit of the lecture. However, there
74 is no holy grail, and flipped-classroom is just one child of the active learning philosophy (Figure 1).
75 Other active learning strategies may be pursued (Jensen, Kummer, & Godoy, 2015) following the

76 same core principles with equal success. They fit with the paradigm of constructivism in learning,
77 where teachers always allow students to construct knowledge in their own way for themselves while
78 advising them (Piaget, 2013). The foundation for constructivism was laid out by the Russian
79 psychologist Lev Vygotsky, who stated that social interaction and learning precedes cognitive
80 development and empowerment (Crawford, 1996).

81 Learning by tutoring has been analyzed favorably early by Bloom (Bloom, 1984) (Figure 1).
82 The next evolutionary step is, let students take over the class - however, supervised. In the literature,
83 positive aspects of FC teaching were shown e.g. for organic chemistry courses (Fautch, 2015). In this
84 work, the focus is a densely monitored transformation of a traditional to a flipped classroom (<25
85 students) in the STEM³ disciplines during the semester term and how this change is received by the
86 MSc students using qualitative and quantitative evaluation.

87 In perspective, active learning methods may also be customized successfully to large
88 classrooms of 45-85 students (Klegeris & Hurren, 2011). Also, the productive use of new media
89 inside the active classroom leads to the “active digital classroom” concept (Hwang et al., 2015).

90 This work contributes to the research field of SoTL by proposing re-conceptualizing means
91 and a new process and evaluation framework to transform TT to new teaching formats (here: FC),
92 while especially continuously monitoring the reception of the transformed teaching format before
93 and after each lecture, and comparing FC vs. TT lecture reception. Additionally, TAP (teaching
94 assessment protocol) interviews were conducted mid and end semester term (Angelo & Cross,
95 2012). The work was carried out in the SoTL (Miller-Young & Yeo, 2015) program at the University
96 of Luebeck, Germany.

97 This paper is organized as follow: 1. The instructional TT and FC course format is presented
98 in the material and methods section. 2. The study design section lays out the continuous and final

99 evaluation methodology. 3. The results section shows the results following the study design. 4. The
100 discussion and conclusion close the paper.

101 **Materials and Methods**

102 The lectures topic was “Virtual Reality in Medicine”. This was a course with technical STEM³
103 character, where data structures and algorithms for the visuo-haptic virtual reality simulation of
104 medical interventions such as needle punctures were taught (Mastmeyer, Fortmeier, & Handels,
105 2016; Mastmeyer, Wilms, Fortmeier, Schröder, & Handels, 2016). Lecture time was two hours (core
106 lecture time: 90 min.) in the middle of the week. Another 90 minutes beyond this study and same to
107 both teaching formats were spent end of the week in on-site exercises elaborating the content of the
108 lecture. Four homework letters with a return time of two to three weeks were issued during the
109 semester. Students teamed up in pairs to solve them. 50% of the homework scores granted
110 admission to the final oral exams. A new micro-feedback loop per lecture was implemented: A
111 questionnaire was handed out to the students to be filled in two parts. The first part was answered
112 before the lecture, the second afterwards. Some question items were paired. Semester mid-term, the
113 educational objectives were TAP assessed (Angelo & Cross, 2012).

114 The aim of a 31 items questionnaire was to get instant feedback at the beginning and end of
115 each lecture. All questions asked before the lecture, have counterparts after the lecture to allow for
116 instant comparison how a lecture was perceived and allows adaptations and steering of the course
117 format and content by the teacher. At the time, the questionnaire was handed out in paper format
118 and digitized to tables by a scanning system.⁶

119 **The Traditional Instructional Course Format (TT)**

120 TT was given in seven weekly lectures. PowerPoint slides with the dual function of serving as script
121 for home studying were read in TT format by the teacher using a laser pointer. Activating quiz

122 elements were used as breakpoints to trigger thinking and motivating oral students' contribution to
123 the course.

124 **The Flipped-Classroom Course Format (FC)**

125 New totally activating teaching was introduced in the second set of six weekly lectures. The
126 upcoming lectures PowerPoint slides were distributed by an institutional Moodle-web-system to the
127 students one week ahead. Study groups were defined to team up and identified a team speaker. At
128 the time, they were congruent to the homework teams. They were provided a weekly doodle-poll
129 (Figure 2) to vote for the part of the lecture they want to take over next week.

130 The classroom featured a projection screen, a projector, and tables arranged in a U-
131 formation with 24 seats. Generally using self-coaching capabilities of group dynamics, a number of
132 four groups with six heads each could be regarded as maximum still enabling to deliver effective
133 coaching. At the opening of the U, the projection screen was installed. A long whiteboard was
134 available at one side of the U. The student with the teaching role stood between the top of the U
135 and the whiteboard pointing with a laser pointer to the screen. With the advent of bringing in own
136 devices for lecture talk preparation, the teacher and the learners created a collaborative learning
137 situation, a so called active classroom (Meyers & Jones, 1993).

138 The time ahead of the lecture with the students already possessing the lecture material
139 served for questionnaire part 1 (B), final material-related questions and the emotional preparation to
140 take over the role of the teacher. The study groups' workload was standardized by assigning an
141 equally fixed number of slides to each group. Group number separation slides for the groups were
142 inserted into the lecture material by the teacher, i.e. title slides with title "FC Group 1" to "FC
143 Group N" (Figure 2). The days after the just held lecture were used by the study groups to vote their
144 next week's part. Particularly, the lecture format was augmented by these detailed elements:

145 1. Questionnaire Part 1 (TT and FC) – Before each lecture: The **B**-part of the questionnaire
146 (Table 1) consisting of 10 Likert items was filled in. These items were repeated and mixed for
147 dispersion with other questions only occurring in questionnaire part 2 (A).

148 2. Instant Feedback Loop Part 1 (TT and FC): Educational goals had been defined by the
149 students at home and were written to the whiteboard in the first 15 minutes before the actual lecture
150 start (c.t.-time⁴). The teacher occasionally refined the delivered goals and discussed and refined them
151 concisely with the students.

152 4. Off-site Flipped-Classroom preparation and Student Presentations (FC only): Each study
153 group was in charge of their slide section and home-made preparation of the lecture slides
154 presentations. The task of the teacher was coaching the study groups and providing tips and useful
155 insight into difficult parts of the slides and how to present them skillfully. Thus, the teacher's role
156 was coach, backup and member of all groups, stepping in for a missing group member or if (ever)
157 an oral delivery went insufficiently. After a group presentation, a one to two minutes discussion and
158 feedback panel were held.

159 5. Continuous Small Oral Exam Simulations (TT and FC): On some occasions using
160 questions arising during the course of the lecture or stemming from quiz-elements (integrated into
161 the slides), students were picked by the teacher to contribute to the questions answer on the
162 whiteboard. This way, a transparent situation simulation regarding the final oral exam was provided
163 to the students. Furthermore, the active contribution and the switch to the FC format was also
164 encouraged in the TT lectures.

165 6. Instant Feedback Loop Part 2 (TT and FC): The defined educational goals from 2. were
166 reviewed in a Q&A again at the end of the lecture. Thus, the students and the teacher got instant
167 feedback, how the lecture was digested. The teacher was then able to eventually re-elaborate on
168 some picked topics in the 90 minutes on-site exercises at the end of the week.

169 7. Questionnaire Part 2 (TT and FC) – After the lecture: The list of 20 A-questions (Table 2)
170 to be answered in the 15 minutes **after** the lecture was handed out to the students and filled in while
171 the lecturer was de-installing the laptop and beamer presentation. For dispersion, ten A-questions
172 were not paired to former part 1 B-questions in this part of the questionnaire.

173 **Study Design**

174 The 12 head study population consisted of 8 male and 4 female master students. The age
175 distribution was 25.17 ± 1.95 and they had quite a history of numerous lectures in TT format. To
176 compensate to some degree for a small but yet sufficient number of subjects, the number of
177 questions was set high and some redundancy in the questions was introduced.

178 The questionnaire that was handed out to the students partly before and after the lecture is
179 shown in Table 1 and Table 2. Questions addressed **cognitive**, **affective** and **didactical** categories.
180 To enable **objectivity** and personal data protection, study member identification a pseudonym
181 signature was used and the factor **Student** is not pursued in monitoring and to the end of this study.
182 Each student filled in the answers using a memorized nick name re-used in each lecture. The
183 (formerly frontal) lectures slide material was enough for max. 24 students in FC teaching format, i.e.
184 min. ca. two slides per speaker. Here, the FC student group size was two, which is preferable as it
185 coincided with the homework submission groups and off-site lecture preparation was considered
186 homework - instead of more homework letters.

187 Regarding statistical **reliability**, the micro-feedback questionnaires in two parts per lecture
188 delivered enough Likert data samples (4692) on a six level Likert scale (Matell & Jacoby, 1971) to
189 conduct statistical procedures meaningfully with enough power for the main factors (format, time
190 point), i.e. vs. a small number of degrees of freedom in the model formulation (Ryan, 2013). For
191 increased **validity**, a Likert scale with an even number of items was chosen, to provoke a clear
192 decision in the middle of the scale. Obviously, dedicated monitoring questions concerning the FC

193 format were not answered in TT lectures (A29, A30) except lecture 9. Especially, the negative
194 question A29 served as general monitoring question and sequence bias test against stereotypical
195 answering.

196 The second questionnaire part repeated some questions (pairs) from Table 1 and introduced
197 new items (Table 2) for distraction and more valuable information. The before-after question pairs
198 are shown in Table 3. The paired Likert items define comparison pairs to be analyzed post-hoc.

199 The purely qualitative, standardized TAP questions (I) and a supplementary question (S)
200 were worded:

201 T00. What helps learning most in this course?

202 T01. What makes your learning more difficult?

203 T02. What suggestions do you have for improving on the obstacles?

204 S04. What do you think about using FCL right from the beginning of the lecture term?

205 The answers to the questions moderated without the lecturer present were noted,
206 condensed, counted and weighted in the TAP vote and are presented synoptically in the results.

207 **Main Effects Analysis**

208 Two main two-level factors were used: Flipped-Classroom (**FC**=Y or N with >2088 samples), and
209 before and after the lecture (**B/A**=B or A with >1560 samples) from multiple questions.

210 The measured variable was the Likert score between 1 (fully disagree) and 6 (fully agree). In
211 this work, the ordinal scale motivated the author to use the generalized linear model family in SPSS
212 while keeping SPSS's default independent structure working correlation matrix and an "ordinal
213 logistic" model type (Lawal & Lawal, 2003). To further cope with the taken repeated measurements
214 structure, in a "Generalized Estimating Equations" (GEE) framework (Loeys, Cook, De Smet,
215 Wietzker, & Buysse, 2014) **Student** was chosen as subject variable, while **Lecture** and **Question**
216 served as within-subject variables for ordering the Likert score measurements. Main effects and two-

217 way variable interactions were considered along the research questions and for model sensitivity
 218 reasons. Iterative elimination of highest insignificant interactions from the set of all two-way
 219 interactions was carried out (Carey, 2013). The most cascaded (*) and insignificant interactions were
 220 eliminated first, and then the model fit was run again after each term elimination step.

221 Covariate factors instead of fixed factors were chosen when an ordering could be applied
 222 and the number of value realizations was greater than four. The pursued research questions to be
 223 answered with a focus on the dichotomic **FC** fixed main factor were:

224 1. Is there statistical difference in the main, or covariate effects?:

225 **FC,**

226 **B/A, or**

227 **Lecture,**

228 **Question.**

229 2. Is there a two-way interaction effect (*) especially for **FC** with the other variables, e.g.:

230 **FC * B/A,**

231 **FC * Lecture,**

232 **etc.**

233 The main effect factors therefore are “before”, “after” (**B/A**) the lecture, “traditional” vs.
 234 “flipped” (**FC**), and factor interaction between **B/A** and **FC**, i.e. especially if the resulting Likert
 235 scores were higher with **FC=Y**.

236 In summary, an univariate multifactorial general linear model was used with repeated
 237 measurements (general estimating equations, GEE) consisting of subject and within subject
 238 variables. The model was chosen along the research questions and with respect to all two-factor
 239 interactions with high sample power. Instead of standard deviations, the broader error bars with
 240 confidence intervals (CI-95%) are shown in the descriptive profile plots.

241 **Detailed Assessment of B/A-Question Pairs**

242 In the paired question comparison stage, SPSS's Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk (Yazici &
243 Yolacan, 2007) tests for normality for question groups B00 to A30 were carried out first. Based on
244 the normality test results, the Friedman ANOVA followed by post-hoc Wilcoxon-Signed-Rank tests
245 for the outlined question pair differences (Table 3) and for **B/A** question pairs was used. Post-hoc
246 and most conservatively, Bonferroni correction is alternatively given for a more conservative
247 judgement in the narrative of results and discussion of this text (Armstrong, 2014). More sensitively
248 and considering the independence of each question pair, the involved test groups are pre-selected
249 and independent with their own H_0 and used only once each, i.e. not in a complete two-combination
250 family of tests as in usual combined post-hoc testing, where there is a joint group null hypothesis.
251 Still for the conservative reader, the strict Bonferroni levels p_B are also shown in the tables. Many
252 important p -values for the affective question domain still were significant also with conservative
253 levels.

254 The statistical software platforms were IBM SPSS 26 (Armonk, NY, USA)⁵ for testing and
255 descriptive plotting. JASP 0.11.1 was used for some descriptive plotting, where convenient. Linear
256 model based descriptive 2D profile plots' error bars are CI-95%.

257 **Results**

258 **Qualitative Observations**

259 As expected, the teacher observed the students partially as passive listeners during the first half of
260 the semester. They were occasionally playing on their smart phones. During small exam simulations
261 carried out in both traditional and flipped format, the students took a big step in presentation skills,
262 especially when the flipped-classroom was activated. They were shy and unsecure dealing with the
263 small exam simulations in the first part of the semester. When actively integrated in the course of

264 the lectures, the use of smart phones and the shyness vanished. They developed a keen interest in
265 providing their share to the lectures without the teacher interrupting.

266 One student's significant and astonishing quote in one of the first FC lectures was:

267 "Please do not interrupt my talk in the middle, I have my own way of presenting
268 these thoughts and I have been preparing and thinking through this at home."

269 On this occasion, the teacher was happy to hear about the commitment of this student and
270 from now on only jumped in at the end of the student's presentation, eventually triggering a small
271 discussion or adding some missing details if needed. Note, the need for discussion or additions
272 diminished towards later lectures in the FC half of the semester as the students grasped the
273 elements important to the teacher quickly. Finally, even difficult slides with up to one-minute video
274 footage or difficult system overviews were presented fearlessly and successfully by the students.

275 In the first FC lecture (7), the TAP interview with vote counting (**N**) was answered by
276 students as follows (abstentions were not counted)

277 T00. What helps learning most in this course?

278 (4) "Interactive lecture."

279 (2) "Small group size."

280 (2) "Practical examples."

281 (2) "Discussions are also possible during the lecture."

282 T01. What makes your learning more difficult?

283 (3) "Slides as the only way to prepare."

284 (2) "Often no references."

285 (2) "Different use of (technical) terms."

286 (2) "Sometimes incomprehensible explanations."

287 T02. What suggestions do you have for improving on the obstacles?

288 (3) "(Lecturer should) indicate own sources (in the handout slide material)."

289 (3) "Link to further material (clickable link)."

290 (2) "Lecturer should step in if not all information has been given by the student."

291 S04. What do you think about using FCL right from the beginning of the lecture term?

292 (3) "Without additional material some slides are too much (difficult)."

293 (2) "Flipped-Classroom also means more time and less content."

294 (2) "Too much workload (if fellow students are absent)."

295 **Quantitative Analysis**

296 **Main Effects Analysis**

297 The final significant variables and interactions kept in the GEE model were:

298 **FC,**

299 **B/A,**

300 **Question,**

301 **Lecture**

302 and the interactions:

303 **FC * B/A,**

304 **FC * Question,**

305 **FC * Lecture,**

306 **BA * Question.**

307 The results show significance and corresponding high Wald-Chi-Squares (effect weights) for
308 the main effects and their interactions (Table 4).

309 The questions with index >9 (A) were filled in after each lecture, others (B) before.

310 Generally, there is a tendency to better Likert scores towards the last question (Figure 4).

311 Interactions with **Question** were significant (Table 4). Thus, in conclusion there are significant

312 effects for **Question**. Individual question pairs will be compared later in this section for the factors
313 **FC** and **B/A** (cf. details in Table 5 and Table 6).

314 *Flipped-Classroom (FC) and Interactions with other Variables*

315 The comparison of frontal vs. flipped-classroom teaching (**FC=Y**) shows highly significant results
316 (Table 4, Figure 5 and Figure 6). This is also detailed post-hoc per question in Table 5 and Table 6.

317 More importantly as main effects are outshined by interactions, the interaction of **FC*B/A**
318 was significant (Table 4). The profile plots in Figure 5 and Figure 6 with CI-95% error bars show a
319 strong uptrend and angulation (interaction) with increased confidence (smaller error intervals).

320 The interaction of **FC*Lecture** is significant (Table 4). The intergroup separation is shown
321 in Figure 7. **FC*Question** was significant, too and the interaction profile is shown in Figure 8. So,
322 individual questions were supposedly answered much better with **FC=Y**.

323 The remaining interaction **B/A*Question** (Figure 9) was significant, but is not in the
324 research focus of this work and is rather only kept for significant effect model formulation
325 completeness.

326 *B/A*

327 There is significance to higher scores after (A) the lecture, especially interacting with **FC=Y**. This is
328 shown in Figure 5. Variable interactions show significance (Table 4 and Figure 5). Concluding and
329 obviously for the variable itself, there is a significant effect for B/A.

330 *Lecture and Question*

331 FC lectures, were rated differently by the subjects. This is depicted in Figure 3. There is a clear trend
332 towards better scores with FC teaching. Interaction with **Lecture** and the variable itself is
333 significant. **Question** was involved in significant interactions, so it is a significant factor even if it is
334 not as a main effect in Table 4 (Carey, 2013).

335 **Comparison of Individual B/A Question Pairs and Splitting by FC=Y/N**

336 The question group data samples were tested for normality with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and
337 Shapiro-Wilk test which both failed highly significantly. Friedman ANOVA yielded $p < 0.001$, so
338 significantly differently answered question pairs were present. Wilcoxon-Signed-Rank tests were used
339 as post-tests (not a post-hoc test family) for all **FC** question pairs (Table 5) and selected cross test
340 pairs as shown in Table 3 (Table 6). Bonferroni correction $p_B < 0.05/10$ is provided for conservative
341 readers (Armstrong, 2014). As there is an independent one to one mapping of groups, i.e. by the
342 predefined pairing, every group is used only once in the comparisons (Table 6). So, the results are
343 shown in Table 6 also with normal significance levels. The layout of Table 6 corresponds cell-wise to
344 Table 3, augmented by three-fold in-cell information in separate lines:

345 1st cell line: overall B/A difference,

346 2nd cell line: B/A subgroup difference with **FC=N**, and

347 3rd cell line: B/A subgroup difference with **FC=Y**.

348 Some question pairs show significant differences before vs. after the lecture (Table 6).

349 Further splitting the total group into **FC=N** and **FC=Y** subgroups, yields a Friedman
350 ANOVA result of $p < 0.001$ for the total and the **FC=J** group. Afterwards, different answers B01-
351 A11, B07-A20 are detected by Wilcoxon-Signed-Rank tests. For the **FC=Y** subgroup, a $p < 0.001$ is
352 achieved with the Friedman ANOVA test. As detected by Wilcoxon-Signed-Rank tests, differences
353 B02-A12, B03-A16, B04-A17, B05-A18, B06-A19, B07-A20, B08-A21 and B09-A24 are significant
354 (all except the first two question pairs). This is summarized in Figure 9 and Table 6.

355 **Discussion and Conclusion**

356 The transformation of frontal to flipped classroom teaching was a success story and allows for
357 fruitful comparison of the two teaching formats.

358 Obviously for **Question**, different questions provoked different Likert responses which is
359 due to the different topic of the questions and the interactions, such as **Question*B/A** (Figure 4,
360 Figure 5 and Figure 9). **Lecture** was a significant factor, also due to its significant interactions, too.
361 As the content of the lecture was different and also the format varied, clearly this is a significant
362 factor. More relevant than the conclusions regarding the main effects are the interactions itself.

363 The main research question here regards the factor **FC** and its interactions. In Table 5 the
364 significance levels are shown for the classrooms with **FC=Y** vs. **FC=N** (cf. Figure 8). Bonferroni
365 correction $p_B < 0.05/31$ is only optionally applied here (Armstrong, 2014), as there is an independent
366 one to one mapping of groups, i.e. by the predefined pairing, every group is used only once in the
367 set of comparisons. B00 to B02 as well as A10 to A13 and A28 concerning the learning goals or the
368 “red thread” show significance. A-questions were answered slightly better. In this part of the study,
369 the interpretation is that the FC format activates the students’ positive course experience and their
370 own thinking about the didactic targets, even if the learning goals discussion was kept in both
371 formats. B03, B06 as well as A16 to A19 (n.s., but more confident votes for **FC=Y** in Figure 8)
372 being about future benefits show uptrends, too. Hence, the feeling of the students with regards to
373 FC lectures is positively inclined. A13 and A15 indicate that the FC lecture was better tailored to the
374 learning goals and prepared the students better for the homework. A20 was about the skill to convey
375 the learning goals to others and in an exam situation.

376 Moreover, significance was found for all interactions with **FC**. This leads to the important
377 conclusion of **FC** itself and its interactions being significant model effects (Table 4). The Wald-Chi-
378 Square weight of **FC** is also dominant in this analysis. The significant items A23 and A24 reflect on
379 the didactic methods used and their explanation by the teacher or students’ on-the-job grasping their
380 sense. With the mind-activating FC format, this could be successfully achieved easily. The paired
381 question of A24, i.e. B09 in Table 6, was not significant as being asked before the lecture and

382 students being indifferent at this time (Likert: 3 or 4). The questions concerned about didactics, i.e.
383 the learning environment and the emotional atmosphere: A25 to A26, showed significant benefits
384 for the FC format. Thus overall, the new format was well received by the students also in terms of
385 human factors (soft-skills). A27 and A29 (n.s., but confident vote for **FC=Y** in Figure 8) confirmed
386 that a trend towards feeling burdened by switching to the new format was perceived (A29). This
387 could be attributed to the perceived increased workload in students' activated minds compared to
388 TT.

389 The interactions analyze the inclines in Likert scores depending on joint variables. The
390 obvious side interaction without an important research question in this paper **B/A*Question** was
391 significant and thus was kept in the model fit (Figure 9). The important interaction **FC*BA** was
392 significant (Table 4, Figure 5 and Figure 6). This could be attributed to the increased confidence
393 (smaller error intervals) with **FC=Y** and the higher knowledge gain after a lecture at the same time.
394 Second, along the research lines, the interaction **FC*Lecture** stands out (Table 4, Figure 7). The
395 significant interaction **FC*Question** contributes with a relatively low interaction to the model
396 (Table 4, Figure 8). Figure 8 shows many upwardly directed and crossing connections, and some
397 significant differences for individual questions were indicated (Table 5). The negative monitoring
398 question A29 is the only item resisting in the lower Likert values. So, the students received the new
399 format, when better knowing it, as a burden. This fact could be attributed to behavioral change
400 towards a new kind of teaching, some starting problems as indicated in the qualitative TAP results
401 and the necessary rewiring of students' brains – stated exaggerated: FC is not watching TV with
402 learning procrastination to the end of the semester.

403 Looking at Table 6 with selected pair-wise comparisons of question pairs using rank-based
404 methods and Figure 9, there are many significant differences found for **B/A**, even if Bonferroni
405 levels apply (Table 6: First cell line #s). This attracted further investigation, especially for the

406 subgroups concerning **FC**. B00-A10 was not significant overall as the discipline of announcing
407 learning goals and discussing them at the end of the lecture was kept in both teaching formats.
408 Except the first two questions pairs, all paired items were significant and the task was to clarify what
409 was the origin of the significance. Further splitting the groups into **FC=N** and **FC=Y** subgroups
410 revealed more details. While in the subgroup **FC=N**, **B/A** comparisons were only rarely significant
411 (B1-A11, B7-A20), consistent significance was detected for the **FC=Y**, **B/A** comparisons except the
412 first two pairs (third cell line). The interpretation here was that the factor **FC** causes a steep incline
413 in Likert scores as also can be seen in Figure 6, Figure 7 and Figure 8. Thus, supposedly the personal
414 gain for the students was clearly higher using the FC teaching format.

415 This can also be discussed looking qualitatively at some of the individual **B/A** cross
416 compared questions:

417 B02-A12: The learning objectives are firmly anchored in my memory.

418 There was a significant difference before and after the lecture, especially when the flipped-
419 classroom format was used. This supposedly means, FC helped the students to memorize and think
420 about the teaching objectives in a deeper way.

421 B03-A16: I feel I am well prepared for the exercises.

422 B04-A17: I have the feeling that I am well prepared for the homework.

423 B05-A18: I feel I am well prepared for the exam.

424 B07-A20: I can convey the content to others, especially in the exam situation.

425 The felt preparation level for exercises mainly from the affective question category,
426 homework and final exam is significantly higher with **FC=Y**. This is a good sign of the effectively
427 increased and active thinking triggered in the students. For B7-A20 and **FC=N**, there was
428 significance. So, also the traditional lectures did a good job. However, for **FC=Y** highly and

429 Bonferroni significant differences showed out. This again underlines the better impact of FC
430 lectures for the final exam situation.

431 B06-A19: I have the feeling that the event has brought me something for the future (e.g.
432 further study, job, personality development).

433 B09-A24: I can profitably take didactic methods from the event for my (possibly) own
434 teaching (e.g. as a tutor, later as a lecturer)

435 The perceived use of the lecture is clearly higher for FC lectures. The conveyed skills do not
436 only cover the reproductive and deductive use of a knowledge base, but also soft skills such as team
437 work, presenting difficult technical topics in front of a group and discussion with a group. There
438 was also a significant effect for FC classrooms regarding the teaching of the new didactic methods
439 just by using them and explaining them occasionally.

440 B08-A21: I think about my own learning and control my learning activities myself.

441 While in a passive **FC=N** setting, no self-monitoring of learning activities was triggered
442 before vs. after the lecture, there is a significant impact for FC classrooms. This proves the activation
443 of students once more.

444 As indicated, Bonferroni correction or similar post-hoc test methods were only optionally
445 applied here to make the discussion more explanatory and sensitive (lively) vs. the observed effects.
446 The adjustment of significance levels for test sets is part of current discussions in the statistics
447 research community (Armstrong, 2014). The conservative reader might want to apply the
448 Bonferroni levels, which are provided as well in Table 5 and Table 6 (#).

449 From the teacher's and a student's perspective, the students' amount of (home-)work was
450 greater than in traditional lectures (A29) – classroom preparation was added to the regular
451 homework exercises. In the author's opinion, a fine-tuned balance has to be found here and it might
452 be advisable to reduce the regular homework load inherited from a TT format during a

453 transformational semester. In this study, many students got their admission for the oral exam from
454 the reduced homework results in the middle of the semester.

455 In conclusion, the comparison of a traditional to a flipped-classroom was a success.
456 Remarkably, the students were very motivated and once insisted that the teacher does not interrupt
457 during their presentation to finish their delivery. Statistical significance for the main factors and their
458 interactions was proven using a repeated-measurements generalized linear model (GEE) with a
459 correction term for “ordinal logistic” scales (i.e. the Likert scale) regarding questions mainly from
460 the cognitive (facts) and affective levels (emotions) vs. the introduced FC teaching. Significant factor
461 constituents were then analyzed in detail with rank-based statistical methods as the normality
462 assumption for general linear models (ANOVA) was hurt. Finally, the FC classroom format reaches
463 out to offer significant benefits, i.e. increased mind activation levels, to the students, possibly even if
464 a mixed format lecture course (traditional & flipped) is offered. In this class of course, a quality
465 driver was the final oral exam at the end of the semester.

466 For the future, it would be interesting to implement the lecture with larger scale classrooms,
467 to investigate the topic of pure FC format lectures more closely, and which results show with
468 written exams at the of the semester violating constructive alignment, which is sometimes inevitable.

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471 especially Daniel Wiswede and Jonas Obleser, all also affiliated to University of Luebeck, Germany.

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Footnotes

¹ <https://www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/education/why-um/problem-based-learning>

² <https://mdprogram.mcmaster.ca/mcmaster-md-program/overview/pbl---problem-based-learning>

³ STEM: Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics academic disciplines

⁴ c.t.: from latin, cum tempore, 15 minutes, colloquial “the academic quarter”

⁵ <https://www.ibm.com/analytics/spss-statistics-software>

⁶ <https://www.cogniview.com/pdf-to-excel/pdf2xl-ocr>

⁷ <https://tatp.utoronto.ca/teaching-toolkit/ci-resources/cdg/lesson-design/active-learning/>

483

Tables

484 Table 1

485 Part I of the questionnaire asked before (B) the lecture. Colour coding: blue: cognitive level (facts); yellow:
 486 affective level (emotions); green: didactic level (learning environment).

Lecture No.: _____ Flipped-Classroom: y / n Pseudonym: _____	fully	disagree	rather	rather	agree	fully agree
Likert-value	1	2	3	4	5	6
B00. The learning objectives were defined together at the beginning of the lecture.						
B01. I can explain the learning goals in my own words.						
B02. The learning objectives are firmly anchored in my memory.						
B03. I feel I am well prepared for the exercises.						
B04. I have the feeling that I am well prepared for the homework.						
B05. I feel I am well prepared for the exam.						
B06. I have the feeling that the event has brought me benefits for the future (e.g. further study, job, personality development).						
B07. I can convey the content to others, especially in the exam situation.						
B08. I think about my own learning and control my learning activities myself.						
B09. I can profitably use didactic methods from the event for my (possibly) own teaching (e.g. as a tutor, later as a lecturer).						

487

488

489 Table 2

490 The questionnaire part II asked after (A) the lecture.

Lecture No.: _____ Flipped-Classroom: y / n Pseudonym: _____	fully	disagree	rather	rather	agree	fully agree
Likert-value	1	2	3	4	5	6
A10. The learning objectives were discussed at the end.						
A11. I can explain the learning goals in my own words.						
A12. The learning objectives are firmly anchored in my memory.						
A13. The lecture is tailored to the educational objectives.						
A14. The learning objectives are covered or mirrored in the exercises and home exercises.						
A15. The homework exercises were solvable with the material of the lecture and exercise (without using google).						
A16. I feel I am well prepared for the exercise.						
A17. I have the feeling that I am well prepared for the homework.						
A18. I feel I am well prepared for the exam.						
A19. I have the feeling that the event has brought me benefits for the future (e.g. further study, job, personality development).						
A20. I can convey the substance to others, especially in the exam situation.						
A21. I think about my own learning and control my learning activities myself.						
A22. The used didactic methods were explained.						
A23. I know why certain didactic methods were used.						
A24. I can profitably use didactic methods from the event for my (possibly) own teaching (e.g. as a tutor, later as a lecturer).						
A25. The atmosphere has encouraged learning.						
A26. The environmental conditions were appropriate for the learning of the group.						
A27. The learning success is in good proportion to the extent of self-activity.						
A28. The entry into the lecture is facilitated by an overview ("red thread").						
A29. The flipped-classroom method is not an additional burden for me.						
A30. Flipped-classroom helps me prepare for the oral exam format.						

491

492 Table 3

493 The corresponding items asked before (B) vs. after (A) each lecture.

	<p>I can profitably use didactic methods from the event for my (possibly) own teaching (e.g. as a tutor, later as a lecturer).</p> <p>I think about my own learning and control my learning activities myself.</p> <p>I can convey the content to others, especially in the exam situation.</p> <p>I have the feeling that the event has brought me something for the future (e.g. further study, job, personality development).</p> <p>I feel I am well prepared for the exam.</p> <p>I have the feeling that I am well prepared for the homework.</p> <p>I feel I am well prepared for the exercises.</p> <p>The learning objectives are firmly anchored in my memory.</p> <p>I can explain the learning goals in my own words.</p> <p>The learning objectives were defined together at the beginning of the lecture.</p>									
A \ B	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
10	x									
11		x								
12			x							
16				x						
17					x					
18						x				
19							x			
20								x		
21									x	
24										x

494

495 Table 4

496 Tests of Model Effects conducted with general linear model (GEE) and repeated measurements. $p < \text{Sig.}$ Table
 497 from IBM SPSS 26.

Tests of Model Effects			
Source	Type III		
	Wald Chi-Square	df	Sig.
FC	56.247	1	.001
BA	6.632	1	.010
Question	.100	1	.752
Lecture	12.295	1	.001
FC * BA	17.244	1	.001
FC * Question	9.548	1	.002
FC * Lecture	32.882	1	.001
BA * Question	4.770	1	.029

Dependent Variable: Likert score

Model: (Threshold), FC, BA, Question, Lecture, FC * BA, FC * Question, FC * Lecture, BA * Question

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502 Table 5

503 Comparison of questions for the factor **FC=Y** vs. N using Wilcoxon-Signed-Rank tests. N.s.: not significant;
 504 *: $p < 0.05$; **: $p < 0.01$; $p_B < 0.0016$ (two-tailed).

Q \ FC	$p <$	Significance
B00 - B00	0.017	*
B01 - B01	0.011	*
B02 - B02	0.017	*
B03 - B03	0.018	*
B04 - B04	0.058	n.s.
B05 - B05	0.058	n.s.
B06 - B06	0.028	*
B07 - B07	0.14	n.s.
B08 - B08	0.079	n.s.
B09 - B09	0.147	n.s.
A10 - A10	0.011	*
A11 - A11	0.033	*
A12 - A12	0.007	**
A13 - A13	0.035	*
A14 - A14	0.084	n.s.
A15 - A15	0.011	*
A16 - A16	0.016	*
A17 - A17	0.026	*
A18 - A18	0.016	*
A19 - A19	0.009	**
A20 - A20	0.026	*
A21 - A21	0.119	n.s.
A22 - A22	0.071	n.s.
A23 - A23	0.023	*
A24 - A24	0.048	*
A25 - A25	0.014	*
A26 - A26	0.018	*
A27 - A27	0.033	*
A28 - A28	0.016	*
A29 - A29	0.317	n.s.
A30 - A30	1.000	n.s.

505

506

507 Table 6

508 The corresponding before (B) vs. after (A) items and post test result: n.s.: not significant;
 509 *: $p < 0.05$; **: $p < 0.01$; #: $p_B < 0.005$ (Bonferroni); ***: $p < 0.001$ (two-tailed). First cell row: overall B/A; second
 510 row: **FC=N** subgroup; third row: **FC=Y** subgroup. Statistical test results with IBM SPSS 26.

A \ B	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
10	n.s. n.s. n.s.									
11		n.s. *								
12		n.s.	***#							
16			n.s. **	**#						
17				n.s. **	***#					
18					n.s. ***#	***#				
19						n.s. ***#	***#			
20							n.s. ***#	***#		
21								*	***#	
24									**	n.s. **
										*
										n.s. *

511

Figures

512

Bloom's Learning Pyramid Turned over:

513

514

Figure 1: Bloom's taxonomy revisited⁷ (Bloom, 1965, 1984). Students in action promote better recall of knowledge. The active learning method "FC teaching" exactly fosters the beneficial areas as well as the approach of constructive learning (Piaget, 2013), where students are responsible how they "do" achieve the goals under some supervision.

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Flipped-Classroom Voting Poll Set-up:

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521 *Figure 2.* flipped-classroom voting pol set-up with doodle.com. Reading direction: Top left to bottom right.
 522 The link to the poll: <https://doodle.com/anonymous> can be used in the invitations by email to the team
 523 speakers of the study groups.

524

Likert Scores during the Course of Lectures:

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527

Figure 3. Likert scores provided after the FC started with lecture 7. There is a trend to better Likert scores to the end of the semester. Underlying model from Table 4. Plots are done with JASP.

528

Likert Score vs. Question:

Error bars: 95% CI

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530
531
532

Figure 4. Questions answered before and after (>9) each lecture. There is a mild trend towards higher scores at the end of the lectures except negative question A29, which aims at FC as additional burden for students. Underlying model from Table 4. Plots are done with JASP.

533

The Interaction Plot of the Factors **B/A*FC** vs. Likert Score:

Covariates appearing in the model are evaluated at the following values: Question = 14,80, Lecture = 8,76

Error bars: 95% CI

534

535 *Figure 5.* Likert scores provided after the before/after (B/A) the lecture. There is a trend to better Likert
 536 scores at the end of a lecture and an interaction with FC. Underlying model from *Table 4*. Plots are done with
 537 SPSS.
 538

539

The Interaction Plot of the Factors **FC*B/A** vs. Likert Score:

Covariates appearing in the model are evaluated at the following values: Question = 14,80, Lecture = 8,76

Error bars: 95% CI

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Figure 6. Significant interaction of factors **FC*B/A**: In the generalized linear model preferred here, there is a trend to better Likert scores for FC lectures and after a lecture. White dots=0=before the lecture. Black dots=1=after the lecture. Underlying model from *Table 4*. Plots are done with SPSS.

544 Descriptive plot of the Factors **FC*Lecture** vs. Likert Score:

545 *Figure 7.* Significant changes for the variable **FC*Lecture**. There is a strong trend to better Likert scores for
 546 FC lectures. Lecture 9 (grass green) was given in TT format, once in the FC period. Underlying model from
 547 *Table 4.* Plots are done with SPSS.

549

550

Descriptive Plot of the Factors **FC*Question** vs. Likert Score:

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Figure 8. Significant influence of factor combination **FC*Question**. In the generalized linear model preferred here, there is a trend to better Likert scores for FC lectures. Only the negative question A29 is a low outlier. Underlying model from Table 4. For uncluttered plots, see Appendix *Figure 10*. Plots are done with SPSS.

555

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Descriptive Plot of the Factors **B/A*Question** vs. Likert Score:

Non-estimable means are not plotted

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Figure 9. Significant influence of variables **B/A*Question** augmented by **FC** in the lower diagrams. In the linear model, there is a trend to better Likert scores after lectures. Confidence intervals indicate the spread of the Likert scaled answers to the questions (vertical lines) in the per question stacked plots. The bottom right outlier A29 (green) was found again to be differently answered here. Underlying model from Table 4. For uncluttered plots, see Appendix Figure 11. Plots are done with SPSS.

563

564

Appendix

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Detailed descriptive Plots of the Factors FC*Question vs. Likert Score:

566

567 *Figure 10.* Significant influence of factor combination **FC*Question**. In the generalized linear model (GEE)
 568 preferred here, there is a trend to better Likert scores for FC lectures: $p < 0.02$. Confidence intervals are
 569 omitted in the overview above to increase readability of the plot. Plots are done with JASP.

570
571

Detailed descriptive Plots of the Factors B/A*Question vs. Likert Score:

572

573 *Figure 11.* Significant influence of variables **B/A*Question** augmented by **FC** in the lower diagrams. In the
 574 generalized linear model (GEE), there is a trend to better Likert scores after lectures: $p < 0.029$. Confidence
 575 intervals (omitted above) indicate the spread of the Likert scaled answers to the questions (vertical lines) in
 576 the per question plots below. White dots: FC=N, black dots: FC=Y. The outlier B00 was not found to be
 577 differently answered to A10 (bordered circles). Plots are done with JASP.

578

3D Scatter Plot of the Variables Lecture vs. Question vs. Likert Score:

579

580 *Figure 12.* 3D scatter plot of the variables **Lecture** vs. **Question** vs. Likert score. Lecture 9 in traditional
 581 teaching format inside the cluster cloud of the FC lectures is clearly visible. For better display, binning with 8
 582 scale levels was used in SPSS.

583

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